

INNOVATION AND TECHNOLOGY:
THEIR ROLE IN MANAGING
INFORMATION OF ORGANIZATIONS

INTRODUCTION

Innovation plays an important role in all the facets of business including developing products, managing information, changing the culture of management, and reinventing operations and human resource activities among others. Organizations which adapt to change quickly consider innovation as one of the most vital aspects of business because of its evident contribution to the development and coordination of the market. (Tohidi & Jabbari, 2012) The value of innovation in competitively positioning an organization and its brand in the market is almost inalienable if done perfectly.

The emergence of various technologies, including revolutionary digital tools and methodologies that aim to assist the business world in improving operations, information management, and connection and interaction with stakeholders has impelled private, non-profit, and public organizations to raise the bar high when it comes to innovating offered products and services. Social networking sites, mobile computing, big data, and other digital-based technologies have continuously influenced the society and the economy- leading to increased competition and pressure to and among organizations in developing new capabilities and transforming organizational culture. (Snow, Fjeldstad & Langer, 2017)

Applying the advantages brought about by innovation and technology, more and more organizations are acknowledging their importance in managing their information. The concept of using innovation and technology has helped organizations to establish competitive advantage when it comes to enhancing their processes (http://file.scirp.org/pdf/IB20110400005_80489624.pdf), particularly, in handling information and how it can easily flow from one user or area to another. A good example is the cloud which

has opened new opportunities to e-services in providing great flexibility and storage in managing and computing information via the internet. (Youssef, 2012)

As information becomes vast and intricate, the need to understand the value of information technology and concept of innovation becomes more imperative. Their role to information management must be clearly defined so that appropriate action plans will accommodate their contribution to managing information as a key factor in decision making in an organization. (Karim, 2011)

The research focuses on the role that technology and innovation play in improving the system of information management of organizations. This includes understanding the evolution of traditional information management to a digitally based system of storing and transmitting information or what is now called as information system. This also introduces the concepts surrounding technology and innovation that are vital in managing information of organizations. As available technology upgrades, systems to information management must be innovated as well. Globalization and the fast-moving economy demand continuous improvement to the way organizations handle important information. Otherwise, they will fail to address their internal needs and the needs of their customers/consumers.

The proponent believes that the topic has theoretical and practical importance to organizations which are exposed to vast amount of information coming in and out of their system. Practicality wise, this study will introduce new technologies for information management and how most management innovate their way of treating, securing, and handling data. E-commerce, e-government, and e-libraries are examples that this paper will try to explore because of their technological and innovative implications.

The researcher is technically and academically inclined when it comes to computer science and information management- fields which are vital in understanding related studies and literatures that are relevant to the topic. The researcher's background in both fields will help in the successful accomplishment of this study.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

This study focuses on the role of technology and innovation to organization's information management. Specifically, this aims to:

1. Understand the theories and concepts about information technology and innovation;
2. Introduce new technology innovations with respect to information management.
3. The role and importance of technology and innovation to managing information of organizations.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

This research proposal seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How important is technology and innovation to organizations when it comes to managing their information?
2. What specific roles do technology and innovation play in information management when it comes to:
 - a. Improving system efficiency in dealing with data;

- b. Designing and redesigning data flow.
 - c. Information security.
3. What factors/determinants affect the successful implementation of innovation and use of new technology in managing information of organizations?
 4. What can be proposed to promote the culture of innovation and use of technology in managing information?

LITERATURE REVIEW

The proponent of this research has gathered several relevant journals and other academic sources to support and provide foundation to the study. The literature review of this paper focuses on the importance of innovation and technology, the concept and application of management information system, and the emergence of e-services such as e-government.

Importance of Innovation and Technology to Organizations

Innovation is considered as one of the primary forces that helps organizations to boost their competitiveness, stimulate growth, increase profitability, and create customer values. (Ionescu & Dumitru, 2015) With respect to managing information, innovation may help organizations to enhance and develop an information system that is best suited for the nature and size of information they handle. It embraces technological changes which include utilizing methods or inputs new to the company. (Tohidi & Jabbari, 2012) Continuously improving the innovativeness of organizations is dependent upon the behavior of the management which must promote the

value of innovation to the whole organization and to the employees who collaborate to produce success indicators. (Nedelko & Potocan, 2013)

In a study conducted by Ionescu and Dumitru (2015) titled “The Role of Innovation in Creating the Company’s Competitive Advantage”, the researchers acknowledged the role of innovation when it comes to increasing market share, improving the quality of products, acquisition of a new market, and enlarging product range among others. They took note of the positive contribution of innovation to economies around the world to which they mentioned that 53% of European Union companies reported innovation in their organizational activity from 2008 to 2010. The authors discussed that the practice of innovation necessitates a critical mind to come up with unique imagination and creativity. They’ve concluded that enterprises which have commendable innovative activities and technological drive are at the forefront when it comes to developing the economy. Furthermore, the study suggests that economic science shows that organizational stability and progress cannot be achieved by simple investment but needs to back it up with technical improvement through innovation which amplifies the value of capital and human resource. (Ionescu & Dumitru, 2015)

Sulaiman, et. al (2015), concluded in their study that the positive impact of creativity shown through practice of innovation is apparent. The study dictates that the competitiveness of organizations is attributed to the creativity and innovation employed by the latter in dealing with knowledge assets (Sulaiman, Hashim, Ibrahim, Hassan & Oluwatosin, 2015) which includes handling and managing information.

In a study conducted by Read (2000) about Determinants of Successful Organizational Innovation, one of the results revealed that management support is the most frequently identified

determinant of innovation. The author suggested that innovation as a popular managerial concept should be accepted and embraced as a strategy by management to sustain high performance and compete in a global business environment. (Read, 2000)

According to Iqbal et. al (2013), innovation and organizational growth have direct relationship with each other. The researchers concluded, based on analysis of relevant literatures and studies, that innovation and technology significantly affect organizational growth and that the use of both will enable the company to stabilize and increase profit growth, strengthen competitive advantage, survive in maturity stage, and compete in a global environment. ([https://www.arabianjbmr.com/pdfs/OM_VOL_3_\(4\)/3.pdf](https://www.arabianjbmr.com/pdfs/OM_VOL_3_(4)/3.pdf))

Ahmad (2014), in his study titled “Technology in Organization”, discussed that new technologies are prolifically and customarily being integrated to business systems nowadays and are useful in decision making. One of the emphasis of the study is on information related to employee salary such that it stated that technology made salary payment system more convenient to organizations by bank transfer instead of manually giving their salary to them. It conferred that new technologies have made flow of information better and efficient for business transaction. (Ahmad, 2014)

Meanwhile, Shaqiri (2015) in her study “Impact of Information Technology and Internet in Businesses”, introduced electronic business or e-business which the proponent of this study believes is much related to the topic of this research. Shaqiri mentioned that information technology and internet has helped businesses to strategically enter new markets and innovate their products and services. The study referred e-businesses as game changer in the market and economy having information transferred and/or communicated via electronic mail, voice mail,

teleconferencing, and electronic exchange among others. The author concluded that both the use of information technology and internet is a key to innovatively handle information and create new business models that can help organizations progress. (Shaqiri, 2015)

Introduction to Management Information System

Al-Mamary, Shamsuddin and Aziati (2013) promotes the importance of managing information of organization. According to them, the effective and efficient management of information is vital to organizational strategy. The study stated that collection of high quality data leads to high quality, timely, and relevant information that is crucial to the decision-making process of organizations. The study defined Management Information System (MIS) as one of the types of information system that processes data from the organization's systems and convert them to meaningful information to be used for managerial decision making. MIS enhances the quality and value of information which affects the kind of decisions the management makes. (Al-Mamary, Shamsuddin & Aziati, 2013)

A research titled "Management information systems and business decision making: review, analysis, and recommendations" stated that MIS gives the management quick access to relevant information which includes information queries, data mining techniques, interaction with decision support systems, and cross-referencing of external information. The study took note of Kumar's study in 2006 which considered MIS as a fitting platform for managerial decision making and therefore suggested that MIS strategies should integrated in the decision-making process in a way that it achieves business goals. (Nowduri, n.d.)

According to Karim (2011), Management Information System is an integrated user-machine system and is of paramount value because of its crucial role in providing information to support business operations, and effective decision making at all levels of the organization. The study emphasized that MIS should have sufficient data to supply relevant information that is useful to its users. (Karim, 2011)

Emergence of E-Services

The continuous improvement of information technology has opened doors for an electronic revolution that led to the emergence of what is called e-services. The aim of these e-services is to speed up the delivery of products or services while reducing organization cost of doing it. E-services can be classified now into e-ticketing, e-commerce, e-education, e-health, e-education, and the popular trend to government offices- the e-government. (Taherdoost, Sahibuddin & Jalaliyoon, 2015)

In the study conducted by Islam and Scupola (2011), the authors cited that e-services, as technological innovations, are designed and intended to provide real-time accessibility and high-end electronic services to people and organizations with the use of information and communications technologies. (Islam & Scupola, 2011)

In an assessment conducted by Zaida and Qteishat (2012) on e-government service delivery, they revealed that to establish public trust with respect to the offered services of e-government, quality must be prioritized. The study concluded that the quality of e-government services is what influences the impression of citizens to its value. (Zaidi & Qteishat, 2012)

A study about the assessment of the impact of e-government in India revealed that citizens and businesses who were able to be utilized manual and computerized systems of the government overwhelmingly preferred to use the latter in most projects because of the less waiting time which came down by approximately 50%. (Bhatnagar & Singh, 2010) This pretty much sums up the value of technological innovation when it comes to managing information.

Meanwhile, the study conducted by Visser and Twinomurinzi (n.d.) contended that the use of e-government services supports government's service improvement philosophy which means people are prioritized. They suggested that for e-government to become successful, all e-government systems of the different departments of the government must be integrated to one portfolio to be effective for the people to use. (Visser & Twinomurinzi, n.d.)

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

This research employed the qualitative approach in achieving the aims and objectives of the study. Qualitative methods aim to gather and integrate relevant data to a topic. This simply observes or interprets the topic with the purpose of developing a theory. (Rahi, 2017)

A qualitative approach, as a holistic methodology in research, is appropriate in discovering the role played by technology and innovation in managing information of organizations. It is considered as an unfolding model of research that is conducted in a natural setting- enabling the researcher to amass relevant details or data from practical studies or experiences to answer the research problems. It gives the researcher the liberty to investigate, describe, explain, and interpret collected data from his viewpoint which is perfect for the nature of this study. (Williams, 2007)

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